

SMARTPHONE ADDICTION AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS IN KARACHI, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Smartphone addiction, frequently referred to as nomophobia or compulsive smartphone utilization, has emerged as an escalating concern within the nursing student population.

Objectives: To determine the prevalence of smartphone addiction among nursing students.

Methods: A cross-sectional research design was administered, using a convenient sampling technique to select 119 undergraduate nursing students at Jesus and Mary Institute of Nursing and St. James Institute of Nursing Karachi. The Smartphone addiction scale-short version (SAS-SV) validated questionnaire was used as a research tool to collect information.

Results: The study results revealed that 52.1% of nursing students reported symptoms of smartphone addiction, whereas 47.9% did not exhibit signs of addiction. The gender variable did not significantly associated with smartphone addiction score ($p = 0.243$). Similarly, other variables, including residence ($p = 0.121$), job status ($p = 0.768$), and substance abuse ($p = 0.470$), also showed no significant associations. However, a significant association was observed between the academic year and smartphone addiction scores ($p = 0.012$).

Conclusion: The findings of the study indicated that the majority of nursing students were experiencing smartphone addiction. The interventions should be aimed at managing and reducing smartphone use among nursing students. The students should be educated regarding the negative effects of smartphone use on their health. Additionally, students should be encouraged to engage in physical activities and sports as a means to counteract this issue.

INTRODUCTION

Smartphone addiction is closely related to the term nomophobia, which refers to the fear of being without a mobile phone. The usage of smartphones among nursing students and health professionals has increased at an alarming rate. The statistics indicated an average daily mobile usage of approximately five

hours among nursing students. The previous studies indicated that smartphone addiction adversely affects mental and physical health.[1] In today's world, smartphones are considered the most common and effective tool of communication ;they allow individuals to communicate through multiple

mediums such as talking and sending messages, aid in taking pictures and videos, and provide access to the internet for various purposes. The smartphone industry is one of the fastest growing industries in both advanced and developing countries. [2] These days, smartphones are shaping people's lives and changing their lifestyles and habits. The increased use of smartphones among health professionals during clinical practice is considered a major concern for patient wellbeing and excellence of care. [3] The results of cross-sectional study revealed that the prevalence of smartphone addiction was 42.4% among nursing students. The significant associations were observed for factors such as smartphone use duration, daytime sleepiness, and academic success with smartphone addiction. [4] Around 80% of students use mobile phones daily for up to 5-7 hours. The majority of the nursing students use smartphones for messaging, social networking, playing games and visiting websites. Educational activities using smartphones were lower than access to social networks. [5] The previous research study revealed that the students who were addicted to smartphones complained of having pain in their hands, necks, shoulders and eyes. The nursing students also reported headache and burning in their ears. [6] The results of a qualitative study showed that smartphones are considered a significant part of making emotional relationships. The trust issues in interpersonal relationships and behavior related to attachment anxiety were increased due to the smartphone usage. Excessive mobile usage has a negative impact on the interpersonal relations of adolescent. [7] The free available internet and use of mobile phones as a stress reliever are the major contributors to smartphone addiction. The reduced concentration and poor academic performance are associated with high smartphone addiction. [8] Moreover the previous study indicated that significant relationship was found between smartphone addiction and loneliness. [9] The factors such as educational level, GPA, and number of hourly phone checked were significantly associated with nomophobia. [10] The excess usage of smartphones could negatively affect the memory of the users; it may cause digital amnesia. Due to the overuse and dependence on mobile phones, there is a rising threat to the human population of developing digital amnesia. The phenomena of digital amnesia is

also known as atrophy of memory due to the technology. [11] The musculoskeletal disorders were common in nursing undergraduates who were addicted to the smartphones. [12] The objective of the current study is to determine the smartphone addiction among nursing students.

METHODS:

The research study design was cross-sectional. The research was conducted at Jesus Mary Institute of Nursing and St. James Institute of Nursing in Karachi, Pakistan. Target population comprises of undergraduate nursing students. The convenient sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. The estimated sample size of 119 participants was calculated using open epi software, based on test for one sample proportion, the prevalence of smartphone addiction was 10.41%.[13], with 95% confidence of interval, 80% power of test, and 5% margin of error, an estimate population size of 500 participants. The study was conducted From May to June 2025. Inclusion criteria involves Nursing students enrolled in BSN program; shows interest to participate in the study. Elimination criteria involves students from other nursing programs; students who didn't have smartphone. Study Parameters consist of Independent variables: Age, Gender, Academic level, Degree program, Resident, Job Status, Substance abuse and Dependent variables: Smartphone addiction score. Permission for data collection was taken from the principal of both nursing institutes. Informed consent was filled by the research participants. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured throughout the study. The Socio-demographic questionnaire and Smartphone Addiction Scale-Short version (SAS-SV) was used to collect information. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize demographic information. Independent t-test, ANOVA and Pearson's correlation were applied to analyzed data.

RESULTS:

Table 1 showed socio-demographic characteristics of a sample of 119 nursing students. The participants mean age was 23.15 ± 2.15 years. The gender distribution comprised 54.6% males and 45.4% females. All participants were registered in the

Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) program. With respect to the academic year, 33.6% of students were in their first year, 16.8% in the second year, and 49.6% in the third year. In terms of residency, 26.9% lived with their parents, while 73.1% resided in

hostels. The majority of students 74.8% were unemployed, whereas 25.2% were employed. Additionally, 5% of participants reported substance abuse, while 95% did not.

Table 1: Socio-demographic variables (n=119)

Socio-Demographic Variables	Characteristics	N (%)
Age	23.15 ± 2.15	119 (100.0)
Gender	Male	65 (54.6)
	Female	54 (45.4)
Degree program	BSN	119 (100.0)
	Others	0 (0)
Academic year	First year	40 (33.6)
	Second year	20 (16.8)
	Third year	59 (49.6)
Resident	Family	32 (26.9)
	Hostel	87 (73.1.)
Job Status	Job	30 (25.2)
	Jobless	89 (74.8)
Substance Abuse	Yes	6 (5.0)
	No	113 (95.0)

Table 2 showed that 52.1% of nursing students reported symptoms of smartphone addiction, whereas 47.9% did not exhibit signs of addiction.

Table 2: Smartphone Addiction Levels

Smartphone Addiction Levels	Percentage	Scores Obtained
Smartphone addiction	52.1%	Above 31
No Smartphone addiction	47.9%	Below 31

Very weak positive insignificant correlation was found between smartphone addiction score and age. ($r = 0.039$; $n = 119$; $p\text{-value} = 0.671$) (Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation between Smartphone Addiction Score and Age

SAS, Age	N	r	p-value
	119	0.039	0.671

The results of Table 4 examine the association between demographic variables and smartphone addiction scores. The gender variable did not show a significant relationship with smartphone addiction score ($p = 0.243$). Similarly, other variables, including residence ($p = 0.121$), job status ($p = 0.768$), and

substance abuse ($p = 0.470$), also showed no significant associations. However, a significant association was identified between the academic year and smartphone addiction scores ($p = 0.012$).

Table 4: Association of Socio-demographic variables with Smartphone Addiction Score

Socio-Demographic Variables	Characteristics	Mean \pm SD	N	p-value
Gender	Male	34.80 \pm 11.21	65	0.243
	Female	32.31 \pm 11.81	54	
Academic year	First year	29.73 \pm 13.11	40	0.012*
	Second year	32.90 \pm 7.76	20	
	Third year	36.61 \pm 10.68	59	
Resident	Family	36.38 \pm 11.62	32	0.121
	Hostel	32.68 \pm 11.37	87	
Job Status	Job	33.13 \pm 11.00	30	0.768
	Jobless	33.85 \pm 11.72	89	
Substance Abuse	Yes	37.00 \pm 10.69	6	0.470
	No	33.50 \pm 11.56	113	

DISCUSSION

The current study revealed that 52.1 % of nursing students had smartphone addiction, while 47.9% did not had smartphone addiction. Similar results were found in the systemic review; the smartphone addiction among nursing students ranged from 19% to 72%, averaging 40-50%. [14] The current study indicated no significant difference between male and female participants in terms of smartphone usage. Similar findings were found in the research study conducted in China, gender has no significant effect

with smartphone addiction. [15] Moreover this study also revealed that age of the participants were not significantly linked with smartphone addiction. The findings of the previous research study conducted in Pakistan also showed no significant difference in terms of age group of study participants. [16] The current study also showed that no relationship was found between job status and smartphone addiction. In Brazilian research study, no substantial relationship was found between job status and smartphone addiction. [17] However the results of the present

study showed that academic year was significantly linked with smartphone addiction. Similar result was revealed in the cross-sectional study conducted in Pakistan, significant difference was present in terms of academic level among nursing students. [18]. Furthermore this study also showed that place of stay has no significant impact on smartphone usage. The findings of study conducted in India also indicated that smartphone addiction has no relation with resident of the undergraduate nursing students. [19] The substance abuse was also found to be insignificantly related with smartphone addiction in current study. The Egyptian research study found no significant link between substance abuse and smartphone addiction. [20]

CONCLUSION:

The outcomes of the present study indicate that the majority of nursing students are experiencing smartphone addiction. Socio-demographic variables did not show a significant impact on smartphone usage; however, academic level was found to have a significant effect. The targeted interventions should be aimed at managing and reducing smartphone use among nursing students; it is recommended that measures be taken to address excessive smartphone usage. There is a need to educate students about the negative effects of smartphone use on their health. Additionally, students should be encouraged to engage in physical activities and sports as a means to counteract this issue.

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